

BRICS STRATEGIES 3.0

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ABSTRACT

The last decade has presented a new global economic scenario lead by emerging markets. BRICS countries (comprised by Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa) have been at the forefront in this phenomenon. During these years, the real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth of the world (annual percent change - A% c) averages 3,83. And just BRICS countries reached 6,01 (157,02% more); and Advanced Economies - not yet recovered since the last financial crisis - reached 1,6 (47,78%). At the same time - and largely the result of the same phenomenon - many more challenges lie ahead for these countries which still must maintain their growth and find effective ways of sustainability. To that end, they should create global innovation networks involving a new model of economy acting as “drivers”. Such drivers must be conceived understanding global trends. Innovation, vanguard, and adaptation will be key to new era. The importance of this this investigation is defined, analysis of these points and studies them as Strategies 3.0 for sustainability and continuous growth.

KEYWORDS

BRICS countries growth, New Challenges, Drivers to Good Life, BRICS Trends, Era 3.0

1.INTRODUCTION

In 2010, the global financial system remained fragile, but economies around the world began moving toward recovery. Some, especially those in emerging markets, hardly broke stride, continuing their rapid growth. BRICS Countries are leading the growth of the economy in the world, and have done so for over 10 years. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) projected that from 2013 to 2017 it will maintain its growth at least 26% above World Growth GDP. This information comes from the IMF [1] data base and calculations made by the author.

As emerging market countries gain in stature, new companies are taking center stage. The rise of these emerging market leaders will constitute one of the fastest-growing global trends of this decade. These companies or New Emerging – Markets Multinational Corporations (EMNCs) will continue to be great competitors in their home markets while increasingly making outbound investments into other emerging and developed economies. This paper will describe the main winning strategies used by these companies to succeed.

To make matters challenging, innovation and ingenuity cannot be stopped. Era 3.0 is fast approaching! The author of this research refers to the "Age 3.0" or just "3.0" using the term to refer to the "New Internet" [2], still under development, intangible; refers to an age markedly by: artificial intelligence, the web semantic, geospatial, sensory and 3D, which promise to affect and transform all areas of the society we know today. Therefore, the author believes this is the perfect term or connotation to describe the future.

The changing global landscape, lead mainly by the BRICS countries, opened the doors to new opportunities and challenges, a consequence of the huge and rapid growth. Some challenges, which the world are already facing and now are even more present in BRICS countries, for example: “How can we mend the imbalance created by over-consumption and deliver a positive legacy for the future? Business models that embrace a system based on consumption alone are obsolete.” [3]. Fortunately, we are starting to see a subtle shift in culture, a move towards a more transparent, sustainable and, most importantly, meaningful model where people actively consider how to achieve the Good Life. It is, therefore, hardly surprising that people now call for companies to demonstrate that they really do care and demand these attributes in everything from government policies to products and services.

I do believe that in order to develop a more sustainable future the equation that represents the new model as: “driver” should be:

$$\text{PLANET+ PEOPLE+ OPORTUNITY+ MOTIVATION + PROFIT = GOOD LIFE}$$

These factors should be the “drivers” in order to face new challenges and in order to healthily coexist while at the same time enabling us to be responsible towards the environment and all communities, avoiding thereby the chaos that the culture of constant consumption could easily bring about upon the Earth.

The BRICS countries should use these factors as "drivers" in order to face global trends. These factors can be applied globally in some cases but all of them are specifically apply to Emerging Powers. It is important to mention that these are long-term strategies which are currently taking shape (Strategies 3.0).

This paper: (i) analyzes and describes growth in BRICS countries and the main winning strategies used by NMCs to succeed, (ii) explains reasons that support as well as define “new drivers–equation 3.0” (iii) explains global trends that affect BRICS countries “trends 3.0.,” and finally offers some conclusions. All the data comes from Official Institutions, also includes research about recent trends in different topics, as well as own experience; corporate work, and talent mobility and research done by the author about BRICS countries.

2. GROWTH IN BRICS COUNTRIES

The Figure 1, shows the argument that as introduces the research and salient facts may be mentioned; (i) 2003 and 2004, emerging economies (BRICS) began a significant consolidated period of growth (and were already doing so), during these two years, their GDP increased from 5,64 to 7,04 (ii) 2008 (September), the outbreak of the global crisis obviously affects everyone. BRICS fell in 2009 to 1,1 (fall but remain in positive), the world economy: -0,6 and Developing Economies: -3,5 (iii) After the global crisis, very slow recovery in developed economies and promising trend showing the BRICS economies. This graph (figure 1), also evidenced the situation and positioning: BRICS, Advanced Economies and World, from 1991 (since all these countries have data) to 2017, from 2013 to 2017 are projections.

Figure 1. Real GDP Growth (Annual percent change) 1991 to 2017

Considering information about the last 10 years (2003- 2012), the position and growth average for each BRICS country (including the world as well) is: **China: 10,45%, India: 7,76%, Russia: 4,73%, world: 3,83%, Brazil: 3,67% and South Africa: 3,46%**. All of them have correlated well with the “world” result, except China, with a strong first place position, followed by India (See Figure 2).

Figure 2. Real GDP Growth BRICS Countries (Annual percent change) 2003- 2012

However, fast growth in economies with a background of instability might not be sustainable. From a statistical point of view, when deciding whether measurements agree with a theoretical prediction, the standard deviation of those measurements is of crucial importance: if the mean of the measurements is too far away from the prediction, then the theory being tested probably needs to be revised [4]. The following comparison was also done for these economies. (See Figure 3):

Figure 3. Market Instability (Mean Vs. Standard Deviation) 2003- 2012

From these results it can be determined which country seems to have higher or lower levels of uncertainty. From higher to lower, the order is the following **China** and **India** (far away from the rest), then, **South Africa, Brazil, and Russia**. Almost the same positioning reached in its growth.

The new global economic scenario has changed phenomenally in the last decades. Securing a sustained growth in the coming years will be crucial in reducing the level of uncertainty for these countries; therefore, it becomes necessary to implement adequate strategies.

2.1. Major players

Regarding growth in BRICS countries as key players in the above-mentioned phenomenon, we find that the growth of the EMNCs has been remarkable. In 2005, there were only 44 of them on the Fortune's List of the TOP Global 500 firms. In 2010, there were 113 of such companies [5]. Many of these multinational companies work with natural resources and also with new brands which have names such as: Lenovo (China), Mahindra & Mahindra (India), Natura (Brazil), Tata Motors and Tata Global Beverages (India), etc. The aforementioned companies are soon becoming strong competitors.

Without a doubt, they applied different strategies, innovated, adapted and succeeded in a time when the global economy required changes and the developed countries of the world were still very pressed and contracted by the latest financial crisis and did so from countries where a volatile economy and political/social uncertainty is an everyday factor.

It is worth mentioning that they used winning strategies and made them perform to the same level of the global firms that until recently had dominated the market. Four types of strategies defined by [6]; two of them are of the more traditional type and the other ones are new. Four strategies in order to develop and deploy an amazing amount of growth and expansion, as well show Table 1, whose source is the same reference.

Table 1. New Emerging – Market Multinational Corporations (NMCs) Strategies

Consumer Segments and International Expansion			
Strategic Competency		Focus on Similar Emerging Markets (Speedy, Easy, Short Term)	Focus on Dissimilar Developed Markets (Slow, Dificult, Long Term)
	Mechanistic Extension	Knowledge Leverager	Cost Leader
	Dynamic Evolution	Niche Customizer	Global Brand Builder

2.1.1. Cost Leaders

Leverage existing low-cost structures and large-scale volumes to extend their reach into developed markets.

2.1.2. Knowledge Leveragers

Tap their existing resources and knowledge of home consumers and the market to build branded businesses in other emerging markets.

2.1.3. Niche Customizers

Combine their cost advantages in manufacturing with newly developed low-cost R&D capabilities to develop customized niche-segment branded offerings in other emerging markets.

2.1.4. Global Brand Builders

Use their low-cost manufacturing and R&D capabilities to build branded businesses in developed markets—but limit their focus to specific products and segments through a process of focused innovation.

Many emerging market leaders have developed in markets with “institutional voids,” where support systems such as retail distribution channels, reliable transportation, telecommunication systems and adequate water supply simply do not exist. As a result, these companies possess a more innovative and entrepreneurial culture, and have developed greater flexibility to meet the demands of their local and “bottom-of-the-pyramid” customers [7].

They must now - as if it were a small matter - make use of: "Genius and Vanguard" again to face 3.0., where the BRICS Economies should use their innovative ways of doing things in order to make them better than the developed economies did in its moments the major growing.

Avoid past mistakes, facing new challenges and a new society, as well as understanding new drivers and trends will be the key to attaining sustainability. To gain that, the synergy between companies, government, society and industry must be key and it may happen in ways we could not have imagined just a few years ago.

3. NEW DRIVERS – EQUATION 3.0

Since the Industrial Revolution, we have been urbanizing at an exponential rate. Only 150 years ago, we consumed 26 times less than we do today. We have now reached a negative tipping point, where unsustainable lifestyle patterns are impacting and affecting us locally and globally. As, Diane Coyle [8] says: “Many would argue that our relentless pursuit of higher economic growth, indicated through GDP statistics, is at the heart of our current dire circumstances.”

3.1. BRICS Well-being

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) [9] has a Framework for Measuring Well-being and Progress. It is based on the recommendations made in 2009 by the Commission for the Measurement of Economic Performance and Social Progress. The aforementioned recommendations emerge because in recent years concerns have arisen regarding the fact that macro-economic statistics such as GDP did not portray the right image of what ordinary people perceived about the state of their own socioeconomic conditions. While these concerns were already evident during the years of strong growth and “good” economic performance that characterized the early part of the decade, the financial and economic crisis of the past few years has amplified them further. Addressing such perceptions of the citizens is of crucial importance for the credibility and accountability of public policies.

They also defined “Progress.” The progress of society is about improvement of the well-being of people and households. Assessing such progress requires not only looking at the functioning of the system of economy, but also looking at the diverse experiences and living conditions of people. Figure 4, whose source is the same organization, shows us the composition “Individual Well-being (quality of life and material conditions)” and remains a cycle through different types of capital “Sustainability of Well-being over Time”.

Figure 4. OECD Framework for measuring Well – Being and Progress

Notably, of the five (5) BRICS countries, only two (2) have data in the database of the OECD: Brazil and Russia, even though they are not members of the same. This data comprise eleven (11) categories and each has from two to three (2-3) variables that describe: Housing (Dwellings without basic facilities, Housing expenditure, Rooms per person), Income (Household net adjusted disposable income, Household net financial wealth), Jobs (Employment rate, Job security, Long-term unemployment rate, Personal earnings), Community (Quality of support network), Education (Educational attainment, Student skills, Years in education), Environment (Air pollution, Water quality), Civic engagement (Consultation on rule-making, Voter turnout), Health (Life expectancy, Self-reported), Life Satisfaction (Life Satisfaction), Safety and Work-Life Balance (Assault rate, Homicide rate), Work-Life Balance (Employees working very long hours, Time devoted to leisure and personal care) for a total of twenty-four (24) variables. The five (5) first results and/or opportunities with major gaps found, after comparing each of these countries (Brazil and Russian) against the average of the member countries of the organization, can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Brazil and Russian TOP 5 Highest Gap Vs. Avg. OECD Countries

For Brazil the first five (5) major gaps are in the categories: Safety (Homicide and Assault rate), Housing (Dwellings without basic facilities), Income (Household net financial wealth) and Job (Personal earnings) and for Russia are within: Safety (Homicide), Civic engagement (Consultation on rule-making), Income (Household net financial wealth), Housing (Housing expenditure) and Health (Self-reported health). It is important to mention that the most important gaps for both are in the "Safety" category and the variable is "Homicide Rates."

For other BRICS countries, we do not have the information to identify the opportunities related to well-being concerns, but we make an analysis of some of the most common indicators in order to determine some level of satisfaction in society for each country, as follows:

The following is an analysis for each country [10]: (i) distribution of income, reflected in the percentage of shares of income or consumption accruing to portions of the population and ranked by levels (deciles in this paper): highest (more income); lowest (less or no income). (ii) The Gini Index-Lorenz Curve, which represents the distribution of income within a community, plotted with a Lorenz curve, where "0" means perfect equality, and "100" implies perfect inequality. (iii) Poverty; considering the percentage of the population living on less than \$2,00 (which covers the \$1,25 a day at 2005 international prices). This information comes from World Bank data base and calculations made by the author [11].

3.1.1. Brazil

The only South American member of the Group, with a population of 196,7 million in 2011 (last year published). There has been some improvement in the incomes distribution, as well, growth of the economy. Considering data from 1990 to 2009; the 20% highest of the population (people with more incomes) controlled: Averages 62,24% of incomes while 20% lowest just 2,38%. The highest deciles (10-20%) have been going down and the lowest (20%) have been going slightly up. More people are joining the middle class. Concerning poverty, it has consistently improved, however moderately; nevertheless, by 2009 they have 10.8% of its population living in poverty. That means a total of 21,2 millions of people. The Gini Index has descended to 6,35 in the same period of time. This country shows the best results in terms of proportion of improvement.

3.1.2. China

The Asian giant has recently given so much to talk about in terms of growth, with a population of 1.344,1 million. Contrary to economic growth, not so well results exposed, with data from 1990 – 2005 (last available), the 20% Highest of the population control: Avg. 45%, while 20% lowest just 6,58%. Overall, it looks like the lowest 10%-20% of the population is poorer, and the highest 10%-20% just descended somewhat. The Gini index jumped by 10,5 in the same period. Regarding poverty (one additional year of data - 2009), it is clear that there has been a descent

(2,6%), in this country it is equal to aprox. 34,8 millions of people. However, by the last year available it shows 27,2% of its population living in poverty. That means 365,6 millions of people (almost two Brazil).

3.1.3. India

Another Asian populated giant. It shows a huge growth and a population of 1.241,5 millions of people. Concerning income distribution: data of: 1994 and 2005 (years available); the proportion is: 20% Highest: Avg. 41,25% and 20% lowest: just 8,8%. There are no significant changes during the time, except that the highest 10-20% of the population (wealthy people) has been receiving more income. The Gini index jumped to 2,56. Poverty levels have improved (based on one more year of data -2010). However, by the year 2010 it had an amazing 68,72% of its population living in poverty. That means 853,2 millions of people (more than China, which has more population).

3.1.4. Russia

The largest country in the world, with a population of 143 million. Its income distribution, from 1993 to 2009: The highest 20% control Avg. 47,07% of incomes, while 20% lowest 5,96%. In this economy, each decile is closer to each other. The Gini Index descended: 8,27 points. Poverty has decreased. By 2009 the result for “\$1,25 a day” is: 0% and “\$2 a day” is: 0,1%. That means 142,9 thousand people. They show the best result in terms of “absolute numbers” in the BRICS countries.

3.1.5. South Africa:

The newest member of the BRICS group and a country representative of Africa. It had a population of 50,6 million in 2011. Considering data from 1993 to 2009 (last year available), the gap between the highest levels (10-20%) and the rest of the population (48,67 points) is disturbing. Here the proportion is: 20% Highest: 65,85% and 20% Lowest: 2.95%. In terms of poverty, it can be said that it has decreased but not significantly. During sixteen (16) years: 9,7 points. That means that by 2009, approximately 15,8 million of its people (31,3%) still live in poverty.

As a group, considering the last 10 years, the GDP average growth of the BRICS countries is 6,0% and the world's is 3,83%. Meanwhile, for all of them, the highest concentration of income is controlled by a few people. The highest 20% of the population controlled 52,3% of the income and the lowest 20% controlled just 5,3%. The Gini Index Average is 46, and 41,9% of the population is living in poverty, that is means: 1.255,9 millions of people (approximately 18% of the population of the world).

3.2. Drivers 3.0

It is appropriate at this point to remember that the middle class in the BRICS countries has grown and continues to grow at a surprisingly high rate, even to the point that it is stated. “By 2025 as many as 50% of the world's population will have joined the so-called consuming classes and annual consumption in rising economies may hit \$30 trillion, the biggest growth opportunity in the history of capitalism” [12]. Such a claim, it is positive because based on the fact that many people are being incorporated into a better lifestyle and more opportunities but carefulness, nowadays (more than ever) based on: common sense, ethics, recent collapses in the economy, the obvious damage to the environment, and the constant concern for the legacy to the new generations. We must look to do things differently and in order to avoid falling into the temptation of adopting unsustainable patterns of life.

I do believe that in order to develop a more sustainable future, the following equation should drive the trends for the next era, the Era 3.0:

$$\text{PLANET} + \text{PEOPLE} + \text{OPORTUNITY} + \text{MOTIVATION} + \text{PROFIT} = \text{GOOD LIFE}$$

We need a planet to live in, and the planet needs to be inhabited by people who respect it. People need to have access to opportunities, and thereby gain the motivation to find their benefits. We should be a positive change for the future and the more effective way is gain Good Life.

4. BRICS TRENDS 3.0

Global economies are so tightly interconnected that companies, governments and industries will soon be forced to cooperate in ways we could not have imagined just a few years ago.

The BRICS countries should use this equation as "drivers" to cope with present trends of all kinds (socio-economic, business, and technological) and to cope with those trends that are to come or that will be accentuated. Some cases apply globally but all of them apply specifically to all BRICS countries. The above-mentioned strategies are full of technology and/or innovative concepts that function well, and they are certainly part of the strategies for long-term development that must be adhered to in order to ensure continued growth and sustainability for the emerging economies.

4.1. Public-Private synergy

Public and private synergy should be even more crucial in the future. Emerging market countries need to boost social spending on pensions, health care and infrastructure, they also need to improve the effectiveness of their tax administration, as well as invest in telecommunications, transportation, education and housing. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) are likely to become important investment vehicles in these markets [7].

Also mentioned in [13], Public-Private Synergy: Making the Best of Both Worlds. Around the world, citizens are demanding that governments manage their tax revenue with efficiency and thrift. Some government leaders have come to believe that a greater reliance on the private sector is the remedy for the inefficiency in the public sphere. Others support sticking with the status quo, pointing to boom-and-bust cycles and other evidence of the private sector's recklessness. Neither option is satisfactory. It is necessary to transcend this conflict by combining the best of both worlds; this concept of synergy implies more than a PPP. When working in synergy, the government entity contracts with a private supplier to deliver specified services, such as transportation or water, under highly regulated conditions. Separating the executive function from the operational entity improves governance and operational outcomes by letting each sector play to its own strengths. The operational dynamism and efficiency of the private sector is combined with the steadiness and social focus of the government. Roles are clearly divided: strategic decision-making, executive control and pricing are government functions, while operations and service delivery are handled by the private contractor. The government retains final responsibility, acting as a controlling shareholder, similar to a holding company that monitors the performance of businesses entrusted with delivery of specific services. In emerging markets, public-private synergy brings in advanced expertise without risking a governmental loss of control over how the technology is used. At the same time, the fact that operations are executed by a profit-driven private entity circumvents the issues that might arise from possible government inefficiencies.

4.2. New Middle Class

Over the next 15 years, just 440 emerging market cities will generate nearly half of the global GDP growth and 40% of the global consumption growth [12]. In a recent report called Macroeconomic Foresights, The Futures Company said that: “In developed markets, consumers feel threatened by the loss of status in declining economies. In emerging markets, consumers feel threatened by a relentless push into an unknown future because of rapidly growing economies. In both cases, consumers want reassurance, guidance and encouragement.” Either way is a good sign that many people are enjoying better standards of living, but it also brings forth a new society, more informed, with other demands, desires and expectations to be met.

4.3. Greener Life

A global P&G consumer survey [14] bears this out, showing that currently 70% of people want to live a greener life but they don't want to be penalized. The initiative [15], explore the impact of the downturn on people management, The different options and scenarios open to companies will play out during this time of great change. They outline three possible worlds or business models which will coexist in the future. They show three fictitious companies as they look back from 2020. These are: (i) Green World scenario: demands for greater transparency and social responsibility in business have been magnified by the crisis and combine with the call for environmental responsibility already present in the green agenda. (ii) Blue World scenario: increased focus on hard metrics to measure performance and productivity as companies look at a long-term reality of having to do more with less. (iii) Orange World scenario: the opportunity for radical new ways of working, taking the concept of workforce outsourcing and globalization to an extreme model portfolio where people organize their work lives as individual businesses in a highly networked world. Figure 5 shows us details of these three possible worlds or business models. What should leadership companies in BRICS countries do? In which companies do capable leaders want to work? The trend says that the first

Figure 6. 2020: Where three worlds co-exist

4.4. Demographic shifts transform the global workforce

Is the number of workers actually shrinking? [7]. A “demographic divide” will soon arise between countries with skilled young workers and those that face an aging, shrinking workforce. The war for talent will become increasingly acute in certain sectors, especially in areas which require high skill levels and more education. It is important to mention that 65% of the companies around the globe are having problems sourcing critical-skills talent. The problem is markedly acute in fast-growth markets. Why can't companies find the right talent despite the growing ranks of college-educated workers and the high unemployment rate in some of the best-educated markets? Part of the answer has to do with the rising of the skill level needed in the evolving global economy; another element is the failure of the educational systems to produce an adequate base of talent to meet these changing needs. Although educational access is growing worldwide, not enough students graduate with the skills desired by global employers. And also cross-border migration has grown 42% in the last decade, from 150 million to 214 million, with most of the traffic directed toward OECD countries. Dramatic growth of emerging market countries is also beginning to change migration patterns. Although developed markets are still a top choice for working immigrants, we are increasingly seeing reverse migration as well. According to the World Economic Forum, “The return migration of highly skilled workers to their home countries is a growing trend for emerging countries.” “Generation U” and women fill the skills gap and create a new focus on broader segments of the talent pool.

Desperate for workers, many companies will become more accepting of a diversity of employees, particularly older workers and women. The leading US advocacy group for retired people, the AARP, believes that 80% of baby boomers will keep working full or part-time past their current retirement age. The Pew Research Center predicts that Generation U (unretired) workers will fuel 93% of the growth in the US labor market through 2016. Employees should gain more bargaining power. Over the past 20 or 30 years, the bond between company and employee has weakened, even in corporate cultures where loyalty was once prized. But now, as the market turns, skilled employees should benefit. They will want a better understanding of their employment options and a greater say in how work is assigned, assessed, and rewarded. The employer will no longer define the workplace; rather, employees' priorities and preferences will dictate what the workplace of the future will look like, particularly now that technology makes it easier than ever to design a variety of flexible arrangements. Companies operating in aging societies will have to craft methods to engage or re-engage the experienced base of talent. Companies that fail to respond to this change and do not succeed in redefining their employee value proposition will fail to attract, retain, or develop talent effectively.

4.5. Female Factor and Social Capital

The Female Factor should induce and influence a fresh approach to collaboration and creating value. At the same time, business in general is recognizing the twenty-first-century's imperative to maintain a social capital focus. Research was [16] conducted in 2011 of 7,280 leaders (of the most successful and progressive organizations in the world both public and private, government and commercial, domestic and international) and it tested how strong he or she were on the 16 competencies that are most important to overall leadership effectiveness. The research asked, for instance, how good a leader was at taking the initiative, developing others, inspiring, motivating, and pursuing their own development. Table 2, shows the results. As leaders in organizations look hard to find the talent they need to achieve exceptional results, they ought to be aware that many women have impressive leadership skills. According to [17], “closing the gender gap can drive long-term economic growth - pushing income per capita 14 % higher than baseline projections by 2020, and as much as 20 % higher by 2030.” Nurturing a balanced gender culture to inspire the best in people in terms of contribution, innovation and loyalty, while ensuring optimal conditions for their individual happiness, is vital to the future success of our society.

Table 2. The Top 16 Competencies Top Leaders Exemplify Most

Competencies	Male Mean Percentile	Female Mean Percentile	T Value
	48	56	-11,58
	48	55	-9,45
	48	55	-9,48
	48	54	-8,84
	48	54	-7,94
	49	54	-7,53
	49	54	-7,15
	49	53	-6,14
	49	53	-5,41
	49	53	-4,48
	50	52	-2,53
	50	52	-2,47
	50	51	-0,78
	50	51	-0,76
	50	51	-0,11
	51	49	2,79

4.6. Global Citizens, Talent Mobility (More Inter-Cultural Exchange)

There is no information about the world that can stay safe for long because the best carriers of information, life experiences, etc. (people) are now global. Global Citizens use new technologies as a means to establish personal interest groups and to explore fresh ideas. Flexible, open-minded and attracted to diversity, they seek enhanced interaction and multi-layered experiences with technology as the key enabler of cultural exchange, social networks and brand engagement. The best and brightest talent is prepared to follow their own agenda and opportunities wherever they may be, irrespective of who is offering them. Future migration is not only influenced by traditional pull factors, such as job opportunities and wage levels, but also by the desire for personal development and improved cultural and political conditions alongside the provision of a "higher level of service" [18], that is mean good life.

This is a reality. Emphasis will be placed on access over ownership, as they prefer facilitation over "more stuff." Younger Global Citizens are particularly attuned to sustainability issues and expect goods to be produced and delivered responsibly. The business world is in the midst of fundamental change, and in 2020 and beyond, the ability of organizations to manage their global talent efficiently will mark the difference between success and failure. It's a world where the strongest and most sustainable supply of talent is in the East, rather than the West. Talent management will become a key strategic tool which places great management responsibility.

4.7. Good Life

Good Life. "Good Life" is not just a cliché, today there are a host of initiatives, offices, organizations, and public and private institutions promoting balance in the life of the individual and providing a real catalyst in order to achieve more and better results in business life, school, family and society as a whole. Although many economists and politicians still view continuous and rapid growth as the only model going forward, in a better world scenario, clean tech and conscious consumption sit alongside transparency as a core business strategy for long-term growth. This resonates with the Study [19], which shows that 87% of the global consumers want businesses to place at least equal weight on society's interests as on business' interests. In the

same survey, less than a third believe current businesses are addressing societal issues, making this a key differentiator for successful businesses of the future. Economic growth does not necessarily indicate more life satisfaction or, at the very least, it is not the only thing we should be measuring. “Happinomics” is flourishing, as many corporations have realized that they can achieve success and change behaviors by encouraging employees to adopt a mindful approach to work and life in general. Harvard Business School’s course on positive psychology as the catalyst for change is now oversubscribed and is informing a new generation of business leaders [3]. New business concepts, such as financial coaching and “energy makeovers” are just the tip of the iceberg when it comes to delivering Good Life propositions and experiences that engage people in self-improvement and in building the future society they want to see.

4.8. Managing the Business

Vanguard and revised management strategies are needed in organizations 3.0 in BRICS countries

4.8.1. Urban growth cluster

BRICS countries have deployed their national development plans by clusters, mindful of understanding the complexity, low viability and slowness of results that might just do it for the whole country. Business strategy must also be considered in these countries, while taking into account the diversity of consumer preferences, the purchasing power, and the market conditions that can be found within the same region by ethnic group.

4.8.2. Predicting Demand

Timing and geographic matters play a fundamental role in matters of competing for the Emerging Markets. Demand for a particular product or category of product typically follows an S-curve [12], there is a “hot zone” where costumers have enough money to buy a product and a “chill-out zone” in which demand eases. Predicting when and where customers will move into the hot zone also requires understanding of technological, demographic, cultural, geographical and regulatory trends as well as comprehensive knowledge of local distribution networks.

4.8.3. Designing an Ultra Segmentation Strategy

Proper use of the benefits of good technology could help users perform segmentation based on their behavior. Needless to say, deciding how and how much to cater to local preferences requires a deep understanding of customer demographics, preferences, and behavior within the target segments in order to reach them with a dynamic message which can be adapted to suit real-time customer behavior well, and which can offer what most would be interested in at the right time. It is also important how consumers encounter managing products at the point of sale. For instance, almost a quarter of the Chinese consumers that were surveyed said that in-store promoters and salespeople greatly influence their decisions [20].

4.8.4. Innovative to deliver value across the price spectrum

Whether a company sells basic product or service to challenge low-cost local players or seeks to entice consumers to adopt new products and services comparable to global offerings, competing effectively often requires innovating and localizing.

4.8.5. Built brands thought Total Transparency and Trust

Information flies and is everywhere (in value or not), people now more than ever prefer the truth and you can only get their attention or get their engagement if they feel confident. It is important to earn this attention and engagement continuously through openness, consistent performance, and total transparency. Research [21] has shown that the more transparent you are, the more people are willing to forgive if mistakes should happen.

4.8.6. Organize today for the markets of tomorrow

The competition which awaits the New Multinationals (from BRICS Countries) is fierce. There is not a single global company that has not placed these emerging powers within radar. They represent a portion of their investments in the coming years. Both local and global emerging markets coexist; they cannot rely on their past successes because selling today is as important as planning for tomorrow. Strategic planning, risk management, talent development, and operating efficiency is not to be left for later. Plan, Innovate, or Disappear.

4.8.7. Handling Emerging-Market Talent

BRICS growth was very rapid, and difficulty in acquiring qualified talent today is one of the most serious flaws and threats to be overcome. Unskilled workers may be plentiful in emerging societies, but skilled managers are scarce and hard to retain or they are immigrants working in developed countries. In China, barely two million local managers have the managerial and English-language capabilities needed [12]. Emerging Markets should endeavor to multiply the number of leaders tenfold, while at the same time looking for them locally, and/or deploying plans to motivate the return of some of them. The strategies of emerging markets need careful study, and they depend on each case; however, increasing salaries is, at best, a partial solution. They must develop clear value proposals (an employer brand).

4.8.8. Key stakeholders

In government, civil society, and the local media, etc., managing these relationships can effectively have an impact on a company's market access, on its ability to engage in mergers or acquisitions activity, and on the broadening of its reputation

4.9. Technology Trends

Smart Technology and hyper connectivity means that we can control all aspects of our lives like never before and this is fundamentally reshaping the way society is operating. There isn't any area of life today that is not affected by ICT (Information and communications technology). These trends are classified as: socio-economic, technological per se, and business-related. Many technology trends are not necessarily just for the single-user-sector. The categories are just a way to group them by functionality, as shows the research [22].

4.9.1. Socio-Economic

Major socio-economic trends which were identified are: the **aging population** (ICT presents many opportunities with respect to improvement in the quality of life and health care in this population), **attention deficit** disorder (mobility and social networks have increased the available channels to inform, establish contact and service customers and users, increasing the number of hits it receives daily), **smart cities** (the expected increase in the percentage of population living in cities will facilitate the development of advanced technology solutions to facilitate citizen

interaction with urban elements), **life-logging** (the possibilities introduced include technology in order to collect information about the activity of individuals and in order to analyze this data in real time, and this will allow the alignment of the supply of products and services), **crowdsourcing** (as a way of harnessing the potential of innovation, financing and execution of tasks and jobs by massive professional communities), the **BYOD-Bring Your Own Device**- (employees increasingly use their own computers to work, improving productivity, availability and response times) and the **redefinition of working models** (due to the increasing shift in preferences and motivations of professionals and improvement in performance, sustainability, capacity, and corporate commitment to foster ICT).

4.9.2. Technology per se

There are a number of technological trends with different degrees of maturity and expected rates of evolution, among them: **Mobile applications, marketplaces and half tablets** (organizations and companies should take advantage of the new types of interaction that these new devices foster), **environmental interfaces human/ computer interaction (HCI)** (to facilitate natural and intuitive interaction between similar devices as between people in real life), **Internet of things (IoT) & context-aware-computing** (the exchange of information between physical and virtual objects over the Internet will generate new services and business models), **in-memory computing (IMC) - storage class memory (SCM)** (the new generation memory capacity and cost is similar to existing storage systems but with similar performance to the RAM), **extreme low-energy servers** (servers that require less energy and space occupied by systems that require less processing) and **desktop virtualization** (the separation between operating system and physical device or hardware that runs it facilitates the tasks of the IT departments and facilitate the deployment of BYOD).

4.9.3. In business

In order to facilitate analysis and understanding of the environment in terms of the business context, the study groups the main trends of the ICT market in the following categories: **Big Data** (proactive and efficient use of information that affects the organization and which is increasingly dispersed, and which is also growing exponentially in terms of volume, in order to improve the services offered and customer satisfaction), **Mobility** (its impact on organizations will be developed by mobilizing business processes and applications to achieve increased productivity and reduce direct and indirect costs. It will also increase customer and employee satisfaction; moreover, it will generate new business models and integration of current mobile devices such as the central axis), **Social Business** (understanding how to maximize the potential of mobile technologies. Social and collaborative approaches will become compulsory jurisdiction for most organizations seeking to develop the areas of customer relations and marketing), **XaaS: Everything as a service** (we will assist in the development of new business models to be used for purchasing and for consumption technology in which the availability of software and development services **cloud** mode applications will be key parts), **business improvement** (business processes are increasingly fragmented in terms of its components and their participants, business improvement will become increasingly more dynamic and processes will require considerable management capacity and technology investment).

A good example is: Government's Role in Innovation Growth [7]. Governments will become increasingly involved in technology, investing in a broad range of applications (from home-grown innovation incubators to local manufacturing sites that create jobs and manage geopolitical risk). Cloud Computing. Governments are taking the lead; much like the US did in the development of the Internet. In China, the Beijing Academy of Science and Technology has built the country's largest industrial cloud-computing platform, designed to serve small and medium-sized

enterprises in government-supported industries, including biotech, pharmaceuticals, new energy and knowledge-intensive manufacturing. At the same time, governments haven't forgotten their regulatory role. As citizens share more personal data on websites such as Facebook, many governments are considering regulations to protect citizens' privacy and corporations' data.

5. CONCLUSIONS

It's clear that BRICS countries are at the forefront of the GDP growth worldwide, but with growth come more challenges in all areas, including, among others, the inclusion of millions of people into the middle class and likewise into the consumer society, which while indeed necessary, it is also known for its negative effects, one of which is: reaching disproportionate levels. Here begins one of the greatest ethical dilemmas and concerns that must occupy decision makers today and that must be adequately handled in order to achieve a better future. As we start to challenge the belief that personal happiness is dependent on the consumption of stuff, we look to other models for inspiration on how to restructure a society based on different values. Whichever way we look at the current landscape, it is clear that the Good Life is the overriding driver for the future agenda and the social glue that interlinks all the trends. As the trends described in this paper change the ways in which businesses operate, grow and compete, winners and losers inevitably will emerge. The winners will be easy to spot. They'll be the organizations that constantly monitor broad trends in external environments, embrace technology and look for talent everywhere, especially among previously neglected segments of the workforce such as women, minorities and older workers. Everyone has already understood this and is trying to figure out how clean tech fits into their paths for growth and is also trying to make it an integral part of their future strategy.

National governments, meanwhile, are seeking ways to meet growth agendas while reducing cost structures and future debt obligations. As businesses and governments look to the future, they must think deeply about the opportunities and risks presented by the evolving trends, and the driving forces behind them. With a different mindset, they can re-imagine what is possible, discover new ways to do things, and discover how best to do it. Those that succeed may find themselves not just navigating tomorrow's global trends, but actually shaping them. Governments, companies, and individuals play an active role in determining the direction of society through their actions and business sense. Governments and companies which pioneer this approach are already seeing huge benefits and this is influencing how we do business as well as shaping policy in fresh ways. Put simply, profit has to be calculated in an inclusive manner to ensure a positive and sustainable outcome and to ensure the rebuilding of people's trust in business and government.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

To my family and my best good friend, near or far physically, always they are with me!

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